

ISLAMIC BANKING FUNDAMENTALS AND CONTEMPORARY TRENDS

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ABSTRACT

The paper on Islamic Banking fundamentals (Interest Free Banking – IFB) and its Contemporary Trends attempts to understand the Fundamentals of Islamic Banking Concepts, recent trends and explore the Case of Ethiopia in IFB. The Research Approach is Qualitative in nature in gathering and analyzing the various literature from Journals, Newsletters, Finance Organizations and other related sources. Most theoretical models of Islamic banking are based on the mudarabah (profit-sharing) and/or musyarakah (joint venture) concepts of Profit-Loss Sharing (PLS). There are, however, other financial contracts that are permissible in Islam, but not strictly PLS in nature. Such financing contracts, for example, may be based on murabaha (cost plus), ijarah (leasing), bai' muajjal (deferred payment sale), bai' salam (forward sale), and istisna (contract manufacturing) concepts. From the various data analysis, it is found that the four major IFB products are banking, sukuk (bonds), equity and funds, and takaful (insurance). And amongst these products sukuk (Islamic Bonds) are headed towards slower Growth due to various reasons, and there is a need for revision and establishment of IFB oriented Banking and Regulatory Norms in Islamic Banking Countries. The Islamic Banking Industry is impacted by the recent technological revolutions namely Fintech, Block chain and Cryptocurrencies. Crowdfunding approaches and drastic usage of Mobile Devices and Applications also adds to the challenges of providing Innovative Services in the IFB sector.

KEYWORDS: Islamic Banking, IFB, Regulation, Technology, PLS.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The first international Islamic bank founded in Jeddah (Saudi Arabia) in 1974 under the auspices of the Organization of the Islamic Conference (OIC) (KHF, 2013) and soon after, a number of commercial Islamic banks were established in the neighboring countries, such as Dubai Islamic Bank, Bahrain Islamic Bank and Kuwait Finance House (Rethel, 2011). Over the last four decades' Islamic finance and banking has been the fastest growing segment of international financial markets to become a global phenomenon. Islamic banks hold over US\$ 1.3 trillion in assets in more than 70 countries (Warde, 2000), are growing at over 15% annually (Benaissa & Parekh & Wiegand, 2005) and account for over 50% of all savings in the Muslim world (Zaher & Hassan, 2001). The Islamic finance industry is composed of four sectors: banking, sukuk (bonds), equity and funds, and takaful (insurance).

According to Islamic Finance Outlook (IF, 2019), the three main opportunities that could unlock the full potential of Islamic finance are:

Regulatory reforms: The world is moving toward profit and loss sharing through recovery and resolution regime implementation. This is an embedded feature of Islamic finance and yet it proves to be challenging to implement on a large scale. Murabaha Profit Sharing Investment Accounts (PSIAs) and sukuk with contractual obligations of their sponsor will lead the growth.

Standardization: Investors tend to shy away from the uncertainty they are not able to quantify. Therefore, we think that standardization, of legal documentation and Sharia interpretation, is not only important, but is the way forward for the industry to restore its appeal.

Fintech: Fintech can also unlock new avenues for growth and enhance the security of transactions. Crowdfunding is a potential source of growth, especially for SME financings and other risk exposures where banks might not necessarily have the appetite to tap. Block chain technology can help banks conduct their operations in a more secure way.

2.0 OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To Revisit and understand the Fundamentals of Islamic Banking Concepts & Foundations.
- To identify the recent trends in Islamic Banking based on Qualitative Data.
- To explore the position of Islamic Banking in the Case of Ethiopia.

3.0 DIFFERENCE BETWEEN ISLAMIC BANKING AND CONVENTIONAL BANKING

In contrast with conventional banking that only maximizes its profit and intermediary purposes, Islamic banking requires also to increase the prosperity of the society (Yaya et al., 2009 and Dusuki, 2008). This social objective proposed using a special scheme of Qardhul Hasan and establishment of zakat, infaq, and shadaqah institution within the bank. The Qardhul Hasan scheme provides service for the poor and do not have an obligation to pay the fixed marked up the profit margin of the bank nor also to share the profit (Yaya et al., 2009). This function has positive impact to help the government reduce the poor. Rahman (2010) concludes that the interest prohibition also found in Judaism, Christianity, Buddhism, and Hinduism and Dusuki (2008) mentions that the function and operation of the conventional bank in accordance with secularism concept. **Table 1** shows the difference between Islamic and conventional bank.

Table 1- Islamic Banking Vs Conventional Banking (Source: Dusuki, 2008)

Islamic Banking	Conventional Banking
Function and operation based on Quran and Sunnah	Function and operation are not based specific principles of religion
The institution that has goal to balance the profit maximization and social responsibility	Profit maximization
Financing instrument based on asset-backed trading or equity financing with risk-sharing concept	Based on interest
Deposit managed within a profit-loss sharing concept	Deposit managed within interest and guarantee fixed profit decided on the front
Pay zakat	Do not have an obligation to pay zakat

Table 2 - Risks in Conventional Vs Islamic Banks, Source: (European Central Bank, 2013)

Type of Risk	Conventional Banks	Islamic Banks
Credit Risk	Default value at risk	Default value at risk, Income expectation of sharing-based assets
Market risk	Volatility of market variables	A lower degree of market volatility
Liquidity risk	Maturity mismatches and alternative funding sources	Maturity mismatches and alternative funding sources
Operational risk	Hardware/system problems and fraud	Hardware/system problems and fraud, Compliance with Shari'ah rules, fiduciary risk
Legal risk	Compliance with local legal framework	Compliance with local legal framework, Compliance with Shari'ah rules
Capital structure	Level of capitalization	Level of capitalization, Composition of capital instruments issued by IIFS (institution offering Islamic financial services)

4.0 ISLAMIC BANKING PARADIGM& TERMINOLOGIES

In Islam, there is no separation between mosque and state. Business, similarly, cannot be separated from the Islamic religion. The Shariah (Islamic law) governs every aspect of a Muslim's religious practice, everyday life, and economic activities. Muslims, for example, are not allowed to invest in businesses considered non-halal or prohibited by Islam, such as the sale of alcohol, pork, and tobacco; gambling; and prostitution. In Islamic contracting, gharar (uncertainty and risk) is not permitted, i.e., the terms of the contract should be well defined and without ambiguity. For example, the sale of fish from the ocean that has not yet been caught is prohibited. The prohibition of gharar is designed to prevent the weak from being exploited and, thus, a zero-sum game in which one gains at the expense of another is not sanctioned. Gambling and derivatives such as futures and options, therefore, are considered un-Islamic because of the prohibition of gharar.

The basis for the prohibition of riba in Islam may be traced to the common medieval Arabic practice of doubling the debt if the loan has not been repaid when due. This practice in its extreme form had led to slavery in medieval Arabia because of the absence of bankruptcy legislation that protects the borrower from failed ventures. Therefore, the prohibition of riba can be viewed as part of Islam's general vision of a moral economy.

Most theoretical models of Islamic banking are based on the mudarabah (profit-sharing) and/or musyarakah (joint venture) concepts of PLS (Dar and Presley, 2000). There are, however, other financial contracts that are permissible in Islam, but not strictly PLS in nature. Such financing contracts, for example, may be based on murabaha (cost plus), ijarah (leasing), bai' muajjal (deferred payment sale), bai' salam (forward sale), and istisna (contract manufacturing) concepts.

- Murabaha financing is based on a mark-up (or cost plus) principle, in which a bank is authorized to buy goods for a customer and resell them to the customer at a predetermined price that includes the original cost plus a negotiated profit margin. This contract is typically used in working capital and trade financing.
- Ijarah financing is similar to leasing. A bank buys an asset for a customer and then leases it to the customer for a certain period at a fixed rental charge. Shariah (Islamic law) permits, rental charges on property services, on the precondition that the lessor (bank) retains the risk of the asset owner.
- Bai' muajjal financing, which is a variant of murabaha (cost plus) financing, is structured on the basis of a deferred payment sale, whereby the delivery of goods is immediate, and the repayment of the price is deferred on an instalment or lump-sum basis. The price of the product is agreed upon at the time of the sale and cannot include any charge for deferring payments. This contract has been used for house and property financing.
- Bai' salam is structured based on a forward sale concept. This method allows an entrepreneur to sell some specified goods to a bank at a price determined and paid at the time of contract, with delivery of the goods in the future.
- Istisna contracts are based on the concept of commissioned or contract manufacturing, whereby a party undertakes to produce a specific good for future delivery at a pre-determined price. It can be used in the financing of manufactured goods, construction and infrastructure projects.

4.1 Major IFB Definitions & Terms:

Islamic banking:

Islamic banking, according to Sundararajan, (2011) consists of mobilizing funds through non interest bearing deposits and through investment deposits based on "profit-sharing and loss-bearing" contracts and channeling these funds to finance permissible (under the Shari'ah law) investment activities, using various forms of Islamic finance contracts.

Interest Prohibition:

Any positive, fixed, predetermined rate tied to the maturity and the amount of principal that is, guaranteed regardless of the performance of the investment is considered interest and is prohibited. (Iqbal, 2014).

Funding Sources:

1) **Shareholder's Funds:**

An Islamic bank may raise an initial equity fund by following the principles of musharaka (equity participation) under this principle, the capital owners enter into a partnership with the bank by contributing equity in return for a share of banks profit or loss on the basis of predetermined ratio. (Bala et.al, 2009: 23).

2) **Wadiah Saving accounts:**

Islamic bankers divide the conventional savings account into two categories. Savings account and investment account. In the case of investment accounts capital is not guaranteed, neither is there any pre-fixed return. Under the savings account the nominal value of the deposit is guaranteed, but they receive no further guaranteed returns. Banks may consider funding under the savings accounts too, as part of their resources and use it to create assets (Abdul-Gafoor, 1995:14).

3) **Current Account:**

Current accounts are demand deposit accounts kept with the bank on custodial arrangements and are repayable in full on demand. Current accounts are based on the principle of wadia (trust or safe keeping) or amanah (trust), creating an agency contract for the purpose of protecting and safekeeping the depositor's assets. (Iqbal, 2014:154)

4) **Investment account deposits:**

Investment deposits represent the case when the owners of the fund seek a return on their funds and are willing to spare these funds for an agreed period. These accounts also operate on the principle of mudarabah, but the modes of investment of the funds and distribution of the profits are customized to suit the needs of the clients. (Kabir & Lewis, 2007:81).

5) Term Deposits:

A term deposit is a type of arrangement where the customer's deposits are held at a bank for fixed terms. These deposits will be then deposited to a number of investment pools where it will be invested in business activities which are according to the sharia. The money deposited in a term deposit can only be withdrawn at the end of the terms as stated in the contract or by giving a predetermined number of days as the notice. Usually, term deposits are short-term deposits where the maturities are within a period of one month to a few years. The Islamic term deposit is commonly structured based on the commodity murabahah, wakalahun restricted investment and mudarabah general investment (ISRA, 2013).

6) Mudarabah deposit

A mudarabah deposit is a form of investment account. Under this principle, the depositor who acts as *asrabbul mal* (wealth/property owner) deposits his money into the bank which acts as *mudarib* (fund manager) that will subsequently use the money for investment purposes. The distribution of profit between the bank and the depositor is in accordance to a mutually pre-agreed profit sharing ratio. This must be disclosed and agreed up front by both parties at the time of the opening of the account. According to the mudarabah principle, the capital of depositor cannot be guaranteed for any financial loss shall be borne entirely by depositor as the capital provider unless proven negligent or there is a breach of the terms of the mudarabah contract with the bank. This is striking difference between a mudarabah deposit and a *wadiyah yad damanah* deposit where the latter entails capital guarantee while the former does not allow banks to guarantee capital return to the depositor.

The mudarabah deposit can be divided into two types. It is the restricted mudarabah (*mudarabah muqayyadah*) and the unrestricted mudarabah (*mudarabah mutlaqah*). In the first one, the actions of the *mudarib* (fund manager) are restricted. However, it should not be in a way, what would unjustifiably constrain the actions of the *mudarib* in his operations. While the second one, the *mudarib* can employ his own good judgment and has complete authority on the management of the capital entrusted to him for any type of investment activities (ISRA, 2013)

Common Sharia-compliant financial contracts includes (British Embassy, 2015):

- Consumer loan (*Murabaha*): Asset purchased by the bank and sold on to the customer with an agreed mark-up;
- Leasing agreement (*Ijara*): Asset purchased by the bank and leased to the customer over a specified period;
- Joint Venture Agreement (*Musharaka*): Investment partnership in which profit sharing terms are agreed in advance and losses are attributable to the sum invested.
- Equity financing (*Mudaraba*): Partnership financing contract under which one party provides the labor whilst the other provides the capital;
- Advance payment (*Salam*): A contract in which advance payment is made for specific goods to be delivered later.
- Gradual financing (*Istisna*): A kind of Manufacturing Finance where payments are made in stages to facilitate gradual progress in manufacturing, processing or construction.
- Agency Agreement (*Wakalah*): A contract where a person authorizes another to do a certain well-defined legal action on his behalf.

Other commonly practiced financial products:

- Bond (*Sukuk*): Islamic type of bond representing the ownership by the *Sukuk*holders in the underlying asset;
- Insurance (*Takaful*): Mutual insurance. *Takaful* is a risk sharing entity that allows for the transparent sharing of risk by pooling individual contributors for the benefit of all subscribers.

Table 3 - The general Shariah concepts and instruments in Islamic banking (Source: Vrajlal, 2015)

No.	Islamic Banking	Conventional Banking	The mechanism
1	<i>Bai' Bithaman Ajil (BBA)</i>	Deferred Payment Sale	BBA applies when a buyer pays the seller after the buyer has sold the good. The seller pays back to the supplier of the funds the capital with an agreed interest as a lump sum or installments. In this scenario, the borrower picks an asset and the bank pays for it and the owner pays back with an agreed mark-up price. This works well with assets like land or house

2	<i>Bai salam</i>	Spot payment for future delivery, deferred delivery, Forward sale	<i>Bai salam</i> means a contract in which advance payment is made for goods to be delivered later on. The seller undertakes to supply some specific goods to the buyer at a future date in exchange of an advance price fully paid at the time of contract. It is necessary that the quality of the commodity intended to be purchased is fully specified leaving no ambiguity leading to dispute. The objects of this sale are goods and cannot be gold, silver, or currencies based on these metals. Barring this, Bai Salam covers almost everything that is capable of being definitely described as to quantity, quality, and workmanship.
3	<i>Mudharabah</i>	Profit Sharing, Trustee financing contract	<i>Mudharabah</i> is a profit sharing arrangement between an investor and the entrepreneur. Where there is a loss the supplier of the fund bears it. A profit sharing contract where one party contributes his entrepreneurial efforts while the other provides capital. The Entrepreneur and the financier will share profit, according to an agreed ratio in the contract. Any loss is exclusively borne by the financier.
4	<i>Hibah</i>	Gift	<i>Hibah</i> refers to a payment made willingly in return for a benefit received. Example: In savings operated under <i>Wadiah</i> , banks will normally pay their <i>Wadiah</i> depositors <i>hibah</i> although the account holders only intend to put their savings in the banks for safekeeping
5	<i>Ijarah Thumma Bai</i>	Hire Purchase	<i>Ijarah Thumma Bai</i> is normally used in financing consumer goods, especially motor vehicles. There are two separate contracts involved (i) <i>Ijarah</i> contract (leasing/renting) (ii) Bai' contract (purchase)". e.g. if one picks a car of his choice and pays a deposit and asks the bank for <i>Ijarah</i> with a promise of leasing the car. After the lease period the bank sells the car to you

Figure 1 - Contracts under Islamic Law (Source: Vrajlal, 2015)

5.0 ISLAMIC BANKING MODELS

5.1 THE HALIM MODEL

Islamic banking has to be located in the Islamic scheme of things in order to determine the Shariah framework for Islamic banking and finance (Halim, 2008). According to him, Islam is basically divided into three main branches, Aqidah, Shariah, and Akhlaq. Aqidah relates to all matters of faith in Allah s.w.t, the Creator Muslims worship, His characteristics, our fundamental faith in Him and our belief in His commands. Akhlaq deals with the higher behavior of Muslims, his character as required of him. Shariah are the rules Muslims live by coming from two principal sources, the primary and secondary sources. The primary sources will be the textual authority of the Quran and the Sunnah; whilst the secondary sources will be from ijma', ijtihad and qiyas. According to the rules of usul fiqh, ijtihad is further refined into its various categories including, istihsan¹, istishab², saddhara'³, maslahah⁴, and 'urf⁵.

Shariah is divided into two broad categories, namely ibadat and muamalat. Ibadat refers to the rules of worship or in other words man-to-Allah concerns, whereas Muamalat refer to rules of man-to-man relationships. Muamalat is however not specifically confined to economic rules, but encompass also political and social rules. However, in modern times it is more popularly associated with business and commerce so much so that Islamic law of commerce is called Fiqh Muamalat. This is the branch where Islamic banking and finance fits in i.e. under Muamalat (Halim, 2008). However, there is another subheading Islamic banking falls under which is less emphasized and often forgotten and that is Iqtisad Islami or Islamic economics.

The siasi sector is the public sector that establishes the laws and regulations, implement economic policies and manage assets, which are under state ownership. The relevant institutions here would be the government economic departments and statutory bodies whilst the law covered will include commercial, company and tax laws. The Tijari sector is the private sector, which essentially is the muamalat sector. This sector is involved in the creation of wealth encompassing the whole spectrum of economic activities from production to distribution and consumption. The components units of this sector will be the economic company and enterprise units. The laws that will govern this sector will be Fiqh Muamalat, specifically, rules on Mudarabah, Musyarakah, Bai, Bai Bithaman Ajil, Murabahah, Ijarah, Rahn and Kafalah to name a few. Halim relies on the principle of trade to justify debt financing in Islamic banking.

5.2 THE CHAPRA MODEL

The other group led by Chapra, Siddiqui, Sadr, Rosly, Dusuki and Haron to name a few takes the view that Islamic banks should embody the principles as espoused by Islamic economics - the Chapra model (Asyraf, 2008). In other words, like other institutions in the Islamic economy the Islamic banks have an apparent and equal responsibility to help achieve economic justice, fair distribution of wealth, and upliftment of the plight of the poor. In the Chapra model Islamic banking is seen as part of the Islamic economic system. Therefore, as in Chapra's model of Islamic banking it will uphold the objectives of Islamic economics (Chapra, 2008). He outlines four goals and values for Islamic economics namely:

- 1) Economic well-being within the framework of the moral norms of Islam (emphasis on Moral Norms, Shariah or Maqasid Shariah)
- 2) Universal brotherhood and justice (justice in all man-to-man relationships)
- 3) Equitable distribution of income (wide distribution of wealth)
- 4) Freedom of the individual within context of social welfare.

5.3 ISLAMIC BANKING SERVICE MODELS:

- 1) Islamic banking window service: Islamic banking window refers to a situation whereby a conventional banking system provides some of the Islamic banking products or services. In other words, it can be seen as a banking system that meets up only the profit, loss, and risk sharing principle of Islamic banking for some of its products. (Audu and Mika'ilu, 2014).
- 2) Subsidiary/branch Islamic banking service: Shariah compliant products and services are provided only in the specific branch where more target beneficiaries are available. It is a semi-independent office of a bank engaging in banking activities such as accepting deposits or making loans at facilities away from a bank's home office.
- 3) Full-fledged Islamic banking service: On the successful accomplishment of Window based Islamic banking service, Banks may establish Full-fledged Islamic banking branches. Such units are better equipped to fully engage in Islamic investment banking activities, such as underwriting sukuk (bond) issuances or managing Shariah-compliant investment and hedge funds, or to manage its own treasury and money market operations.

6.0 GLOBAL TRENDS IN ISLAMIC BANKING – QUALITATIVE INSIGHTS

6.1 ISLAMIC BANKING PRODUCT TRENDS AND COUNTRY RANKINGS

Based on the report by, Islamic Finance Bulletin (2018), it is estimated that Islamic Finance Assets are likely to reach \$3.8tn by 2022, revision and establishment of Shariah Complaint laws in Uganda, Indonesia, Technology development (Fintech) and projection of less growth in Sukuk Market. According to The City UK (2017), The global Islamic finance market has grown rapidly in recent years. ICD and Thomson Reuters estimate that the global market for Islamic finance services, as measured by Sharia compliant assets, totalled around \$2trn at the end of 2015, up 7.5% on the previous year. The market is currently most developed in Malaysia, Saudi Arabia, Iran and the majority of countries that form the GCC. In terms of assets, outside the Muslim world, the market is most developed in Switzerland, the UK, Hong

Kong and the US. The customer base in Western countries is not necessarily restricted to Muslims; other customers may be attracted by the ethical basis of Islamic finance.

Islamic finance is, however, moving beyond its historic boundaries into new territories. Markets where Islamic finance is developing include:

- Other countries in the Middle East and Africa such as Turkey, Sudan, Morocco, Egypt, Jordan and Nigeria.
- Other Asian countries such as Singapore and China.
- Developed countries such as Luxembourg and Australia, which developed as centers for Islamic finance. The US, France, Germany and the UK each have indigenous Muslim populations of up to 5m; Russia has the largest in Europe with 16.5m. Although Islamic finance assets are still primarily in the GCC countries, engagement with the industry, particularly with sukuk in the UK, South Africa, Luxembourg and Hong Kong is important for further growth and development of the industry.

Islamic finance is developing predominantly in Muslim majority countries, most importantly in Malaysia, GCC, and Iran. Experts predict a slowdown in the growth of the industry, a decrease in profitability, and potentially a decline in the quality of assets. Slower growth is expected in maturing markets such as the GCC and Malaysia, while growth is hoping to accelerate in some non-core, newer markets such as Europe, Russia, CIS, and Africa, as well as in Iran, which will be open to the global economy thanks to the recent lifting of sanctions (S&P, 2017; DIB, 2017a, Thomson Reuters, 2016). **Table 2** below presents three different rankings prepared by Thomson Reuters, Islamic Development Bank, and Islamic Financial Services Board, based on different methodologies (see notes below the Table). In a ranking based purely on the share of Islamic banking assets in total banking assets, Iran and Sudan (where 100% of financial institutions are sharia-compliant) lead the way. In the other two – more complex – rankings, however, Malaysia is ranked number one (K4D, 2017).

Table 4 - Islamic finance country rankings (Source: K4D, 2017)

Country	Islamic Finance Indicator*	Islamic Finance Country Index (IFCI)**	Islamic Banking Share in Total Banking Assets***
Malaysia	1	1	8
Iran	12	2	1
Saudi Arabia	4	3	4
UAE	2	4	9
Kuwait	6	5	5
Pakistan	7	6	14
Indonesia	9	7	21
Bahrain	3	8	13
Qatar	8	9	7
Bangladesh	11	10	10
Sudan	12	11	2
Jordan	10	13	12
Brunei	14	15	3
Oman	5	16	16
Singapore	15	25	34

* “Best developed ecosystem for Islamic Finance”. “The ranking was calculated according to four criteria: i) financial (e.g. size of Islamic Finance assets and number of Islamic Finance institutions); ii) governance (e.g. regulations for Islamic Finance and disclosure index score); ii) awareness (e.g. number of related news articles, Islamic Finance education institutions, research papers, and events); and iv) social (e.g. value of Zakat and charity and CSR disclosure index score)” (Thomson Reuters, 2017: 56).

** Variables used for the purpose of IFCI preparation include: i) number of Islamic banks, ii) number of banking and nonbanking Islamic financial institutions (including Islamic windows); iii) sharia's supervisory regime; iv) Islamic financial assets; v) Muslim population; vi) sukuk; vii) education and culture; viii) Islamic regulation and law (Dubai Islamic Bank, 2017b: 56).

*** Countries ranked 1-15 have "satisfy the criterion of having a more than 15% share of Islamic banking assets as a proportion of their total domestic banking sector assets, and hence are categorised as systemically important" (IFSB, 2017: 8).

Arabian Business (2018), reports that Interest free banking sector registers fifth consecutive year that growth rate has been on the decline and put Malaysia on top of the list of the countries leading the industry globally; While Iran is a close second, Saudi Arabia, the UAE and Kuwait are ranked third, fourth and fifth respectively and Indonesia moved one position up to capture sixth position on IFCI, while Pakistan slipped one position down to become the seventh most influential market in the global Islamic financial services industry.

In 2010 the IILM was established in Malaysia, with the purpose to issue Shari'ah-compliant financial instruments and facilitate cross-border Islamic liquidity management. Membership of IILM is open to central banks or monetary authorities as well as financial regulatory authorities or government ministries or agencies that have regulatory oversight of finance or trade and commerce, and multilateral organisations. The IILM initiative was facilitated by the Council of the IFSB in line with its mandate to a) enhance and coordinate initiatives to develop instruments and procedures for the efficient operations and risk management and b) encourage cooperation amongst member countries in developing the Islamic finance industry.

The Global Finance Magazine (Gfmag, 2018), has identified the Most successful Islamic Banking Institutions Countrywide and is listed below in **table 5** :

Table 5- Best Islamic Financial Institutions 2018 - Country Winners (Source: Gfmag, 2018)

Country	Bank
Afghanistan	Afghanistan International Bank
Algeria	Banque Al Baraka D'Algérie
Bahrain	Al Baraka Bank Bahrain
Bangladesh	Islami Bank Bangladesh
Brunei Darussalam	Bank Islam Brunei Darussalam
Egypt	Abu Dhabi Islamic Bank Egypt
Indonesia	Bank Muamalat Indonesia
Jordan	Jordan Islamic Bank
Kazakhstan	Al Hilal Bank
Kuwait	Boubyan Bank
Lebanon	Arab Finance House
Malaysia	Maybank Islamic
Morocco	Umnia Bank
Nigeria	Jaiz Bank
Oman	Meethaq Islamic Banking
Pakistan	Meezan Bank
Palestine	Palestine Islamic Bank
Qatar	Qatar Islamic Bank
Saudi Arabia	Al Rajhi Bank
Singapore	Maybank Islamic
South Africa	HBZ Bank
Sri Lanka	Amana Bank
Thailand	Islamic Bank of Thailand
Tunisia	Al Baraka Bank Tunisia
Turkey	Kuveyt Türk Katılım Bankası
UAE	Emirates Islamic

6.2 IFB GROWTH TRENDS AND INDUSTRY ACTIVITY

Islamic finance encompasses a wide range of services. Banking, which accounts for nearly 73% of Islamic finance assets, and sukuk (17%) represent the forms of finance that are most well established. Funds (3%) and takaful (2%) account for most of the remainder. More niche products which may have scope for future development include private equity and private wealth Management (The City UK et.al.) According to Malaysian Reserve (2018), some of the major trends that will impact Islamic Finance includes,

Impact of Industry 4.0, Fintech and digital banking:

Highly disruptive technologies such as artificial intelligence, robotics and block chain technologies are a compulsion in today's banking. The banking industry is facing competitive threats from two sets of technology-driven companies that have arisen from this Industry 4.0; one set consists of large technology companies such as We Chat, Alibaba Group Holding Ltd and Apple Inc, and the other set comprises new financial technology (fintech) companies. These large companies have used the loyalty and reputation of their core product offerings such as smart phones, technological gadgets and social media platforms to penetrate and disrupt the traditional product offerings of banking institutions. Digitization projects which are primarily revenue-based innovations or entirely new business lines, such as offering online transactional banking services, Robo-advisors, innovative mobile payments and other similar value-added products and services. The point is, the range of digitization is so diverse, cutting across every market, every product line and every distribution channel.

Value-based Intermediation:

VBI is an attempt to realign the focus of Islamic finance towards creating greater socioeconomic impact. The VBI initiative supplements the Sustainable Development Goals, which cover a wide spectrum of development challenges, including poverty, inequality, climate change, sustaining ecosystem and cities, health and education, among others. To achieve most of these objectives, finance plays a pivotal role to facilitate and intermediate capital allocation.

6.3 ISLAMIC BANKING FINANCIAL TECHNOLOGY TRENDS

According to Forbes (2017), The Islamic FinTech Landscape includes some of the below mentioned ones: Wahed has launched Islamic RoboAdvice with access to Sharia compliant ETFs, Yielders is launching an Islamic alternative asset market place such as property, Ovamba, an Islamic trade finance play, is launching a Sharia compliant Initial Coin Offering (ICO) which allows for fees and risk sharing backed by halal instruments using a token, CBX Unit is a Sharia compliant universal payment system backed by grains, Ethis Crowd is using e-Wakalah (agency contract) and Istisna (contract to construct an asset) contracts that allow for crowdfunding of new real estate developments in Indonesia.

And the other key trends emerging in Islamic FinTech that are worth noting includes, Islamic Digital Challenger banks and Sukuk (bond) ETFs, Murabaha (asset backed interest free loan) instruments around buying and selling goods in addition to Takaful (insurance), Sharia compliant investment Funds, Block chain transforming Islamic finance contracts to smart contracts and cutting costs of services by up to 95% with an immutable record of ownership and assets.

While the majority of Islamic fintech is crowdfunding platforms, there have been recent developments in other forms of fintech, such as Islamic Robo-advice. New initiatives are also flourishing. Examples of other forms and initiatives of Islamic fintech beyond crowdfunding include (The City UK et.al.):

- **Islamic Robo-advisors.** Wahed Invest, a US-based investment advisor, launched an Islamic Robo-advisor called Wahed in June 2017; Farrington Group, a Malaysian investment manager, also launched one, called Algebra, in July 2017.
- **Investment Account Platform.** A group of six Malaysian Islamic banks co-founded their first multi-bank fintech platform, the Investment Account Platform, in 2016 to finance SMEs.
- **Islamic Fintech Alliance.** The Islamic Fintech Alliance was launched in 2016 by eight platform operators: Blossom, EasiUp, EthisCrowd, Narwi, FundingLab, KapitalBoost, Launch good and SkolaFund.
- **Islamic Fintech Hub.** The first global Islamic fintech hub, Future Finance 2030, is expected to be launched by the end of 2017 to encourage expansion of Islamic fintech

7.0 MAJOR BANKS AND INTEREST FREE BANKING PRODUCTS IN ETHIOPIA

In 2008, the Ethiopian Banking Business Proclamation (592/2008) was amended to include a provision for IFB. In 2011, the NBE issued a directive to authorize the business of IFB (SSB/51/2011). Currently, the directive is very broad and does not provide any specificity in terms of product lines, rules and regulations to ensure that the products developed by financial institutions are truly in line with Sharia law. The directive defines the service as the mobilization or advancing of funds undertaken in a manner

consistent with Islamic finance, avoiding the receiving and paying of interest. The licensing and supervision of banking business directives to authorize interest free banking also orders banks not to go past the maximum share of interest free banking business in their consolidated balance sheet without prior approval from the central Bank. Establishing a shariah advisory board and separate financial reports, keeping all data and ensuring the segregation and permissibility activities from conventional banking are also some of the requirements set by the directive to launch the program. But, IFB in Ethiopia only started in 2013, when the Oromia International Bank (OIB) launched its services. Commercial Bank of Ethiopia (CBE) joined the market in October 2013, followed by United Bank, which began providing the service in May 2014.

The current section presents the availability of various interest free banking products of Services of the major Banks namely Commercial Bank of Ethiopia, Oromia International Bank and others. Oromia International Bank (OIB) is the first private financial institution to implement interest-free banking [Islamic banking] in Ethiopia in Sept. 2013, three years after the issuance of the Directive. This was later followed by interest-free banking (IFB) solutions for the Commercial Bank of Ethiopia and the United Bank. The Services are offered on the separate window basis along with the Conventional Banking Services. The services of the Bank under IFB are four: Amanah- keeping money safe on trust, Qerd- a current account that allows transactions with cheques, Mudaraba- an investment account, and Mudaraba Time Deposit Account- where the customer saves money for a fixed period and withdrawal is done on notice, not on demand.

7.1 CASE OF CBE (CBE, 2018)

IFB Background in Ethiopia:

Interest free banking (IFB) refers to a banking business in which mobilizing or advancing of funds taken in a manner consistent with Islamic finance principles and mode of operation that mainly avoids receiving or paying interest through units or windows within the conventional bank that exclusively offers interest free banking services.

The Shari'ah law treats transactions based on interest payments unlawful, or harams/forbidden. Majority of the scholars in Islamic finance and economics argue that the involvement of interest rate or Riba violates the principles of social justice as it intentionally rewards those money lenders without exerting any effort or taking any risk in the transactions involved.

The key issue is that a predetermined profit or income should not be guaranteed to the finance providers without sharing the risks of the ventures or projects financed. Sharing of gains in a given venture should be intimately linked with risk-sharing. Alternatively, the principle dictates that Banks should raise their funds based on Safekeeping or Agency contracts, and bank financing base itself on sales or trading, and leasing which involves substantial risks for both the lender and the entrepreneur using the bank finance. The customer-banker relationship in IFB is not, therefore, based on a debtor/creditor, which is the case of conventional banks.

As the Commercial Bank of Ethiopia (CBE) is licensed by the National Bank of Ethiopia to give these services, it would provide the services at specified windows of selected branches of the bank. Interest free banking is available to all customers who want to make use of the alternative banking service. CBE has a separate and dedicated system that does not mix the movement of accounts in those windows with the regular ones.

Financial Administration

o Profit Equalization Reserve: - is a fund left from Net Income of the pool during periods when the profit to be paid to customers are above market price, which helps to smoothen the regular profit payment to the depositors. In other words, the PER used to improve the returns to the depositors during periods when the pool's [profits are below market expectations. Prices shall be determined based on the supply (deposit) and demand (finance), thus the profit payable shall also vary accordingly

o Investment Risk Reserve: - the pool may incur losses primarily due to unusually large write-offs and/or losses on sale of the pool's investments or financing different products. To absorb or off-set the losses the Banks may create the investment Risk Reserve (IRR) to cover the future investment losses.

o Cash holding & o IFB Special Account

Profit Distribution

The distribution of profit or loss on the Mudaraba Saving Account or Mudaraba Deposit Account is depends on the profit or loss involved in financing the product or investment. Profits are distributed after the bank has collected commission income and other similar incomes for the service of financing.

Table 6- Interest Free Banking Services (**Source:** Commercial Bank of Ethiopia, 2018)

IFB Product	Description
MUDARABA (SAVINGS ACCOUNT-i)	Savings Account-i (Mudaraba) is a Shariah compliant product. Under the concept of Mudaraba. Under the Mudaraba contract, the customer (Rabb-ul-mal) provides the deposit and the Bank ("Mudarib) provides its expertise and skill in relation to the investment of such funds. The profit, if any, is shared between the parties according to the pre agreed ratio, while loss, if any, is borne solely by the Mudaraba investor as the case may be. Customers are allowed to withdraw deposits without any restriction on demand. The Bank can use deposit funds from these accounts to finance any businesses permissible under the Sharia.
WADIAH (SAVINGS ACCOUNT-i)	Wadia is a Shariah compliant product. The product is structured under the concept of Wadia. Under the Wadia contract, the Bank agrees to keep funds for its depositors, and customers are allowed to withdraw deposits without any restriction on demand.
QARD (CURRENT ACCOUNT-i)	Current Account – I (Qard) is a Shariah compliant product. The product is structured under the concept of Qard. Under the Qard contract, the customer agrees to provide funds in the form of loan to the Bank with an undertaking by the later to pay on demand any amount outstanding in the Qard account in part or in full as and when required by the depositor. While the Bank reserves the right to use Qard funds for permissible business financing, no returns whatsoever shall be paid to holders of these accounts.

7.2 OROMIA INTERNATIONAL BANK

The various products of the Oromia International Bank include as below (Oromia International Bank, 2018):

Table 7- Interest Free Banking Services (**Source:** Oromia International Bank, 2018)

IFB Product Category	Products
Deposit Services	Wadia Saving, Amana Current, Labbaik Wadia(For Hajj & Umrah Pilgrimage), Mudarabah Investment Deposit (Unrestricted), Diaspora Wadia Saving
Financing Services	Murabaha Financing, Local Murabaha, Import Murabaha, Merchandise Murabaha
Interest-free, Export Financing Facility	Free of Charge
Bank Guarantee Services	Performance Guarantee, Bid Bond Guarantee, Foreign Employment Guarantee Facility
Others	Import-Export Services (full scale), Local Remittance Service, Foreign Remittance Services, Advisory Services on IFB Business

7.3 UNITED BANK

The services offered under the interest free banking will include deposits in the form of Wadiah and Mudharabah, loans and advances using musyarakah, murabahah, Istisnah, Salam and Ijarah principles, and international trade finance on the base of Wakalah and Kafalah, and many more.(United Bank, 2018).

Table 8- Interest Free Banking Services (**Source:** United Bank, 2018)

IFB Product Category	Products
Interest Free Deposit Products/ Wadiah	Current Al Wadiah, Saving Al Wadiah, andMudharabah Deposit
Primary Mode Financing or Investment Type	Mudharabah, Musyarakah,,
Secondary Mode Financing for Direct Credit	Murabahah, Istisnah, Kafalah, Selam, andIjarah
Secondary Mode Financing for International Banking Operations	Wakalah, andKafalah.

8.0 GLOBAL ORGANIZATIONS FOR INTEREST FREE BANKING

There are two international regulatory bodies in the Islamic finance industry, which have been widely used as standard setting bodies and benchmarks for Islamic and IFB products: The Accounting and Auditing Organization for Islamic Financial Institutions (AAOIFI) and International Financial Services Board (IFSB).

8.1 AAOIFI

The Accounting and Auditing Organisation for Islamic Financial Institutions (AAOIFI) was established in Bahrain in 1991 with the objective of providing standards for the Islamic finance industry. AAOIF protocols can be used as a support to issue standards for IFB. AAOIFI has 88 standards, including 48 Sharia standards, 26 Accounting standards, 5 Auditing standards, 7 Governance standards and 2 Ethics standards. These standards could be used as a basis for putting together IFB policies in Ethiopia.

AAOIFI has over 200 members in more than 40 countries. Members include regulatory and supervisory authorities, multilateral agencies, private sector entities, professional firms and industry associations.

- The examples of countries adopting AAOIFI include: Bahrain, UAE, Jordan, Lebanon, Qatar, Sudan and Syria.
- The examples of countries with guidelines based on AAOIFI include: Australia, Indonesia, Malaysia, Pakistan, Saudi Arabia, South Africa and United Kingdom.

AAOIFI standards have introduced greater harmonisation among Islamic finance actors across the world. The advantage of rolling out AAOIFI-compliant products is that they in line with internationally recognized standards. The products launched have been approved, tested and accepted by the Muslim community. AAOIFI standards seamlessly blend with secular practices. No real disadvantage for complying with AAOIFI standards have been identified at this stage. Several central banks and monetary agencies from secular-based countries have heavily relied on AAOIFI standards to develop their IFB industry.

NBE could also roll out IFB products based on the Malaysian model. This model is also derived from AAOIFI standards, however, their products take a more lenient approach towards the interpretation of Sharia. Malaysia is one of the leading countries in Islamic banking and finance; the country has one of the most advanced Islamic banking systems in the world. The main disadvantage is that the products, which are approved in Malaysia, are not widely accepted outside South East Asia. Using Malaysia as a model for developing IFB products in Ethiopia could raise questions from the Ethiopian communities about whether these products are inherently Islamic.

The last option is to come up with a new set of rules, which are specifically designed for the Ethiopian market. While this may have the advantage of customizing products to the needs of Ethiopia, it will entail a heavy workload, without guarantee on how well these products would be accepted. In this case, NBE could empower the banks by making them communicate appropriately to the consumer the products' Sharia compliant features. This last model will also require a significant amount time and financing to conduct research and feasibility studies on the specific needs of Ethiopia.

8.2 IFSB

The International Financial Services Board (IFSB) was launched in 2002 and serves as an international standard setting body that provides prudential standards and guidelines for regulatory and supervisory agencies to ensure soundness and stability of the Islamic Finance industry including: retail banking, capital markets and Takaful (Islamic insurance). The IFSB has 13 standards, 5 guidance notes, 1 technical note.

As of September 2014, the IFSB comprises of 184 members from 41 jurisdictions, including 32 members from the African continent. IFSB has 55 regulatory and supervisory authorities, 8 international/intergovernmental organisations and 121 market players, professional firms and industry associations. (Source: IFSB)

Several non-predominantly Muslim countries have adopted IFSB rulings, including: China, Hong Kong, Japan, Korea, Luxembourg, Singapore and Thailand.

IFSB Members from regulatory and supervisory authorities in Africa include:

- **Djibouti:** Banque Centrale de Djibouti
- **Libya:** Central bank of Libya
- **Mauritius:** Bank of Mauritius, Financial Services Commission Mauritius
- **Morocco:** Bank Al Maghrib
- **Nigeria:** Central bank of Nigeria, National Insurance Commission
- **Senegal:** Ministry of Economy and Finances Senegal, Banque Centrale Des Etats de L'Afrique de L'ouest
- **Sudan:** Central Bank of Sudan, Khartoum Stock Exchange Sudan, The Insurance Supervisory Authority Sudan
- **Tunisia:** Central Bank of Tunisia
- **Zambia:** Bank of Zambia

IFSB Members from private sector, professional firms and industry associations in Africa include:

- **Egypt:** Al Baraka Bank Egypt, Faisal Islamic Bank
- **Kenya:** Chase Bank (Kenya) Limited
- **Nigeria:** Ahmed Zakari & Co (Chartered Accountants), Lotus Capital Limited
- **South Africa:** Oasis Crescent Capital (PTY) Ltd.
- **Sudan:** Al Jazeera Sudanese Jordanian Bank, Al Salam Bank, Animal Resources Bank, Bank of Khartoum, Byblos Bank Africa Ltd, Faisal Islamic Bank, Farmer's Commercial Bank, Industrial Development Bank, Islamic Insurance Company, Omdurman National Bank, Shiekan Insurance and Reinsurance Co. Ltd, Sudan Financial Services Company, Sudanese French Bank, Tadamon Islamic Bank

9.0 CHALLENGES OF INTEREST FREE BANKING

According to Abraham (2017), Interest Free Banking (IFB) is a recent phenomenon, as a result, there is little empirical literature on the area and some of the major challenges includes lack of awareness, regulatory and supervisory challenges, institutional challenges, lack of support and link institutions, gap in research and development in Islamic studies, lack of qualified human resource. Abiola (2015), summarizes some of the major Legal and Regulatory issues facing Islamic Banking and mentioned in the Forthcoming section: Islamic banks have Insufficient Legal Protection (Because, the existing laws were formulated based on conventional banking systems and no serious attempt had been made to change them, except few cosmetic changes introduced in some aspects in some countries), Jurisdiction – Civil or Shari'ah Court (Confusion exists due to absence of Islamic banking legal and regulatory framework), Amendment of existing laws (Islamic banking laws and regulations should be accordingly amended with consideration for the international standards in order to accommodate exponential growth in Islamic banking), Disparity in Concepts and Practice (Need for better interpretation of Islamic Banking Concepts), Ownership of Underlying Assets (Lack of legal and regulatory framework that would properly address this challenge may render many of Islamic banks' transactions null and void), Lender of Last resort (Islamic banks are rendered financial security disadvantaged and more exposed to liquidity problems than their conventional counterparts.).

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